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Supporting Information for

Directly dating Plio-Pleistocene climate change in the terrestrial record

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Introduction

This Supporting Information includes detailed analytical methods for X-ray powder diffraction (Text S1), energy-dispersive spectroscopy (Text S2), Raman spectroscopy (Text S3), and (U-Th)/He geochronology (Text S4). This file also includes Supporting Figures S1 (sample material, and fragments used for dating) and S2 (XRD spectra), as well as Supporting Tables S1 (bulk mineralogy), S2 ((U-Th)/He data), S3 (XRD instrument parameters), and the captions for Table S4 (Raman data) and Table S5 (XRD data).

Text S1. Bulk mineralogical composition of the ferruginous indurations was estimated by X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) using a Panalytical Empyrean diffractometer (Table S5). About 200 g of representative material was pulverized using a vibratory ring mill. To mitigate preferred orientation effects, an aliquot of the powder was pressed into a back-packed sample holder. Instrument parameters are provided in Table S3. XRD mineral identification used the HighScore Plus (Fig. S2) software and an in-house excel spreadsheet. Semi-quantitative estimates of minerals (Table S1) are based on an integration of matrix flushing and reference intensity ratio.

Text S2. Backscattered electron (BSE) images (Fig. 2a) and chemical mapping (Fig. 2b,c) of polished rock slabs (25*10 mm) were obtained using a TESCAN Integrated Mineral Analyzer (TIMA, e.g., Hrstka et al., 2018). The TIMA instrument is a field emission scanning electron microscope equipped with energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) detectors. Measurements used TIMA's liberation analysis with dot mapping (BSE and EDS step size at 1 and 3 μm), a beam energy of 25 kV, a probe current of 5.4 nA, and a spot size of 79.1 nm.

Text S3. Raman spectra (Fig. 2d, Table S4) were acquired using a Horiba® LabRAM HR Evolution with a 600 gr/mm grating, a Peltier cooled Synapse detector and a continuous 532 nm laser produced by a 100 mW Laser Quantum Torus. Mineral damage by the laser was avoided by adjusting the laser power, monitoring visible change on the surface of the sample and the Raman signal. A 5% ND filter decreased the laser power to 0.05 mW on the sample surface (rock slabs). On rough mineral particle surfaces (vein/cement shards), the laser beam was focused to a width of about 4 μm with a 20X objective (N.A. of 0.46) with a 5% ND filter providing 0.08 mW laser power on the mineral surfaces.

Text S4. (U-Th)/He dating used 100–300 μm large fragments of goethite that were extracted from (i) the veins/cement of metallic to vitreous luster (from the surface of the induration) and (ii) the iron-rich domains of argillaceous zoned cutan structures from polished rock slabs, using a scalpel and tweezers. The fragments were then ultrasonicated in ethanol to remove adhering particles, dried and selected for (U-Th)/He analysis using optical and electron microscope images based on their textural and compositional homogeneity. Selected fragments (Fig. S1a) were individually loaded into niobium (Nb) microtubes prior to He extraction. (U-Th)/He analyses were carried out at the Western Australia Thermochronology Hub (WATCH) facility of the John de Laeter Centre (Curtin University, Perth) following the analytical procedures of Danišik et al. (2013). The Nb microtubes containing the goethite fragments were loaded into an ultra-high vacuum extraction line (Alphachron I) and degassed in a single, 10 min long heating cycle at ~ 450 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ using a diode laser to circumvent possible changes in the composition of the parent isotopes (Danišik et al., 2013). Initial test work prior to analysis demonstrated that this degassing protocol resulted in the complete outgassing of the samples without the need to “re-extract” the samples. Evolved gas was purified using a ‘cold finger’ cooled with liquid nitrogen and a hot (~ 350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) Ti-Zr getter, spiked with 99.9% pure ^3He and introduced into a Pfeiffer Prisma QMS-200 mass spectrometer, next to a cold Ti-Zr getter. $^4\text{He}/^3\text{He}$ ratios, corrected for HD and ^3H by monitoring mass 1, were measured by a Channeltron detector operated in static mode. Evolved ^4He contents (measured in nano-cubic centimeters, ncc) were determined by isotope dilution using a ^3He spike against calibrated ^4He gas standards, with a blank correction check by heating empty Nb tubes using the same procedure. Following the ^4He measurements,

Nb tubes containing the goethite fragments were retrieved from the Alphachron I, spiked with ^{230}Th and ^{235}U , and dissolved in 200 μl of concentrated HCl in Parr bombs heated to 210 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 12 h. Each Parr bomb also contained blank and spiked standard solutions. All solutions were analyzed by isotope dilution for ^{238}U and ^{232}Th an Element XR™ High Resolution ICP-MS. The total analytical uncertainty (TAU) was calculated as the square root of the He analysis uncertainty and weighted uncertainties of the U and Th measurements (Danišík et al., 2013). The raw (U–Th)/He dates were corrected for diffusive He loss using an average correction factor of 10% following the suggestions of Bassal et al. (2022). (U–Th)/He dates were not corrected for alpha ejection (Ft-correction) given the size of sub-sampled goethite specimens; however, an additional uncertainty of 10% (1σ) was added in quadrature to the final (U-Th)/He dates to honor our limited knowledge about the factors potentially affecting the alpha ejection correction in the investigated samples (e.g., U and Th distribution).

Figure S1. (a) Image of the analyzed ferruginous induration showing (b) veins of metallic luster that have been analyzed for (U-Th)/He geochronology (Aliquots V1-V11). (c) Representative image of homogeneous goethite fragment of the vein/cement structures used for (U-Th)/He geochronology. (d) Representative image of heterogeneous fragment that contains inclusions (qtz – quartz; zr – zircon) that was discarded. (e) Backscattered electron image of the cutan showing two areas targeted for (U-Th)/He geochronology (Aliquots C1-X and C2-X; see Table S2).

Figure S2. (a) XRD pattern of the ferruginous induration. (b) Same pattern at different scale with 2θ values of identified mineral phases. (c) Close-up of the interval with the (110) goethite peak used to quantify goethite content.

Table S1. Representative composition (semi-quantitative) of a ferruginous induration obtained using X-ray powder diffraction (XRD).

Phase	Mass %
Quartz	72
Zircon	14
Goethite	5
Rutile	3
Hematite	2
K-Feldspar	2
Anatase	1

Table S2. Results of (U-Th)/He geochronology on goethite fragments.

<i>Sample</i>	²³² Th (ng)	±1σ (%)	²³⁸ U (ng)	±1σ (%)	⁴ He (ncc)	±1σ (%)	TAU (1σ) (%)	Th/U	Raw age (Ma)	±1σ (Ma)	Ft	± (%)	He loss correction (%)	Cor. age (Ma)	±2σ (Ma)
<i>Cutan</i>															
C1-2	0.103	3.3	0.01691	4.0	0.009	6.1	6.6	6.02	1.81	0.12	1.00	10	10	1.99	0.43
C1-3	0.022	6.4	0.00785	3.9	0.004	13.2	13.6	2.81	2.66	0.36	1.00	10	10	2.92	0.90
C1-4*	0.065	3.4	0.01412	3.8	0.004	12.6	12.8	4.55	1.02	0.13	1.00	10	10	1.12	0.33
C1-5*	0.101	3.2	0.00458	4.3	0.003	16.9	17.1	21.96	0.84	0.14	1.00	10	10	0.92	0.33
C2-6	0.045	4.3	0.06277	4.2	0.024	2.9	4.7	0.71	2.73	0.13	1.00	10	10	3.00	0.60
C2-7	0.295	3.0	0.16012	3.9	0.063	1.8	3.4	1.83	2.26	0.08	1.00	10	10	2.48	0.48
C2-8	0.570	3.0	0.13205	3.8	0.078	2.2	3.3	4.29	2.40	0.08	1.00	10	10	2.64	0.51
C2-9	0.008	17.2	0.06928	3.9	0.018	3.4	5.1	0.11	2.13	0.11	1.00	10	10	2.35	0.48
<i>Vein</i>															
V-1*	0.442	2.8	0.04033	3.6	0.080	2.3	3.2	10.9	4.55	0.15	1.00	10	10	5.01	0.96
V-2	0.256	2.8	0.02076	4.0	0.023	3.4	4.1	12.3	2.36	0.10	1.00	10	10	2.59	0.51
V-3	0.192	2.8	0.01632	3.8	0.022	3.9	4.5	11.7	2.96	0.13	1.00	10	10	3.26	0.65
V-4	0.534	2.8	0.04892	4.2	0.047	2.9	3.7	10.8	2.21	0.08	1.00	10	10	2.43	0.47
V-5	0.677	2.8	0.06462	3.8	0.057	2.6	3.5	10.4	2.09	0.07	1.00	10	10	2.30	0.44
V-6	1.699	2.8	0.14493	3.8	0.161	4.2	4.8	11.6	2.43	0.12	1.00	10	10	2.67	0.54
V-7	0.992	2.8	0.11884	4.0	0.099	3.5	4.2	8.3	2.32	0.10	1.00	10	10	2.55	0.50
V-8	0.401	2.8	0.05792	3.7	0.052	3.4	4.0	6.9	2.79	0.11	1.00	10	10	3.06	0.60
V-9	0.619	2.8	0.05562	4.2	0.081	3.0	3.8	11.1	3.29	0.12	1.00	10	10	3.62	0.70
V-10	1.113	2.8	0.14834	3.8	0.143	3.0	3.8	7.4	2.86	0.11	1.00	10	10	3.14	0.61
V-11	0.999	2.8	0.11061	3.5	0.080	3.1	3.8	9.0	1.91	0.07	1.00	10	10	2.10	0.41

TAU - total analytical uncertainty; Raw age - (U-Th)/He age uncorrected for alpha ejection; Cor. Age - (U-Th)/He corrected for diffusive He loss and uncorrected for alpha ejection, but with an added uncertainty related to potential factors complicating the alpha ejection. Asterisk (*) indicates analyses that are rejected as statistical outliers.

Table S3. Overview of instrument parameter used for X-ray powder diffraction.

Parameter	Name/Value
XRD instrument	Panalytical Empyrean
Radiation	Co K α 1.789 Å
Generator	40 kV 40 mA
Angular Range	5 to 77 °2 θ
Time/Step	120 s
Step Size	0.0131 °2 θ
Divergence Slit	1 °
Anti-Scatter Slit	7.5 mm
Slit Type	Fixed
Detector	PIXcel in linear mode
Rotation Speed	60 rpm

Table S4. Raman data, V = Vein shards; X = Cement; C = Cutan; a.u. = arbitrary unit.

(File uploaded separately)

Table S5. XRD data.

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